

Operationalising Typicality and Sustainability

Preliminary Report

Sara Madera Gómez, Andrea Borghini. 28 June 2026. Version 1.0

D4.2 Overview

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AUTHOR(S)	Sara Madera Gómez, Andrea Borghini
REVIEWER(S)	Damien Foinant, Augusto Esteves, Janita Van Dyk
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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	GI	Geographic Indication
ciCH	culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	PC	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission	T[No.]	Task {No.}
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Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
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Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2) is a preliminary report that presents the conceptual and methodological framework for operationalising typicality and environmental sustainability in culinary recipes within the RELISH project. The task was to make two ideas precise enough to be built into RELISH's digital tools: *What makes a recipe typical of a place or culture*, and *What makes a recipe environmentally sustainable?*

The deliverable was led by UMIL for Work Package 4 (WP4): COOKING – Recipes & Applications with contributions from LYFE, CITY, BSC, UNISG, UCC, FA, UDUR and in connection with IST. D4.2 corresponds to Task 4.2 (T4.2) “Operationalising typicality and environmental sustainability in recipes.” The result is a set of criteria preliminarily developed for WP6, 7, and 8 and integrated in D4.7 (Month 27).

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU’s common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

RELISH addresses a pressing challenge for European societies—namely how to transmit culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (cICH) in an era marked by profound environmental transformation and rapid technological change. Young Europeans increasingly seek connections to food traditions as sources of identity and community. Yet, they simultaneously recognise the urgent need for sustainable practices in response to climate change, biodiversity loss and resource depletion. The tension between cultural continuity and environmental responsibility forms the conceptual and practical core of the RELISH initiative.

Within this broader project, Work Package 4 (WP4) is responsible for establishing the intellectual foundations that will enable other work packages to develop meaningful, culturally sensitive and technically robust digital tools.

For **Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2)**, the task is both philosophical and practical: WP4 must articulate what makes recipes “**typical**” of particular places, cultures or traditions, and determine how these recipes can be adapted for environmental sustainability while retaining cultural significance.

These questions cannot be answered through technical means alone. They require sustained engagement with the history of food traditions, the philosophical structure of cultural identity, the cognitive mechanisms of recognition and categorisation, and the ethical dimensions of ecological responsibility.

1.1 Description of deliverable

D4.2 synthesises WP4’s work on typicality from March 2025 to December 2025. It builds conceptual frameworks, methodological approaches and operational criteria that subsequent WPs will translate into computational architectures, user interfaces and recommendation systems. The work is preliminary. It establishes foundations for

further refinement through testing and implementation. Yet, it is also comprehensive, addressing the project's core intellectual challenges.

1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

WP4, under the responsibility of the University of Milan with contributions from LYFE, CITY, BSC, UNISG, UCC, FA, UDUR and in connection with IST, is tasked with organising data that makes explicit assumptions about culinary recipes.

WP4 objectives related to D4.2 include:

- Establishing the theoretical and practical framework from which RELISH operates when dealing with existing research and information related to culinary cultural heritage
- Supporting the UCD approach of the technical partners in the consortium from a cultural heritage perspective by identifying key questions and cultural assumptions that are relevant for RELISH
- To assist partners in the development of key terms for analysis in culinary cultural activities organised on behalf of RELISH
- To identify and engage in conversation with institutional stakeholders in promoting culinary cultural heritage in local, national and at EU level

D4.2 corresponds to the following T4.2 tasks:

- Organising data that makes explicit assumptions regarding culinary recipes, such as their typicality or ways to replace ingredients to address sustainability issues
- Identifying specific connections between environmental sustainability as a complex expression containing multiple dimensions and culinary recipes
- Developing a set of criteria on recipes, typicality, and sustainability for WP7&8.

1.3 Rationale

The task was to make two ideas precise enough to be built into RELISH's digital tools: What makes a recipe typical of a place or culture? and What makes a recipe environmentally sustainable?

Both ideas are harder to pin down than they first appear. A dish that everyone treats as a local tradition may in fact be quite recent, and an ingredient at the heart of a beloved recipe may now be difficult to source in a warming climate.

WP4 approached these questions by combining philosophical analysis with evidence, drawing on academic literature, on conversations with historians and other experts, and on input from project partners gathered in meetings held between March and November 2025. D4.2 explains in full what this work showed about how food traditions are formed and how people come to recognise a dish as typical.

The result is a set of practical criteria that the teams designing the RELISH platform can use. These criteria help identify what makes a recipe typical and suggest how a recipe might be adapted for sustainability without losing its character.

Throughout, we aimed to keep a careful balance respecting the real diversity of European food cultures, while avoiding two opposite mistakes: The first is treating tradition as something fixed that must be defended against any change; The second is flattening Europe's many distinct food cultures into a single uniform standard.

This deliverable focuses on two key dimensions:

- **Typicality:** Characteristics of a recipe that make it recognisable as belonging to a place, culture or tradition
- **Sustainability:** The capacity to address environmental pressures through ingredient substitution or recipe modification while maintaining cultural coherence

The challenge lies in operationalising typicality and sustainability to implement in digital platforms without reducing complexity or imposing uniformity across the diversity of European culinary traditions.

1.4 Frameworks

Based on discussions beginning in March 2025 (Month 3), it became clear that typicality cannot be treated as a straightforward category. The concept proved elusive, too rigid when understood as fixed essence and too vague if conceived merely as whatever communities recognise as “theirs.” Numerous scholarly sources consulted for this work confirm that typicality is historically constructed through political, economic and social forces rather than discovered as an inherent attribute.

Insights on typicality carry methodological consequences. The guiding framework developed here **avoids essentialism** while providing an analytical structure capable

of guiding platform design. Essentialism creates two distinct problems. *Analytically*, essentialism misrepresents the evidence—historical literature shows that the features held to be indispensable to a “typical” dish have changed over time, so any model that fixes a single immutable essence cannot represent how a recipe actually evolves. *Practically*, essentialism causes harm—treating one version of a dish as the only authentic one licenses the policing of who may cook it and how, excludes legitimate regional, diasporic, and adapted variants, and would block the very sustainable substitutions the platform exists to support.

The typicality framework also resists the opposite extreme: denying that the concept has any stable content. Communities do organise recipes around features they treat as central (see D3.5 “Survey on Typicality,” *forthcoming*), and these shared expectations are how people recognise a dish as “theirs” and navigate questions of identity and value. The framework therefore locates these core features in communities’ own recognition practices rather than in the dish itself. Typicality is real as a **relational, socially sustained pattern** rather than a fixed essence.

Sustainability introduces additional layers of complexity. Environmental considerations intersect with culinary identity and can support or threaten cultural continuity, depending on how one adapts, frames, and implements typicality. Climate change already reshapes agricultural zones, alters ingredient availability and forces stakeholders to reconsider long-established practices. Young people living in Europe, RELISH’s primary target audience, demonstrate sensitivity to these realities. They value heritage and typicality but resist narratives that ignore environmental consequences.

1.4.1 *Gastro-fundamentalism*

This report introduces the concept of **gastro-fundamentalism** as a key framework for navigating the previously identified tensions. Through the research conducted for this deliverable, we developed the term gastro-fundamentalism to name an attitude that treats culinary traditions as fixed, pure, or inviolable, and that polices any deviation from a supposedly authentic form. This term names a specific risk that the historical and conceptual analysis in this report repeatedly brought into view. If a digital platform encodes typicality as a rigid standard, it risks excluding the very communities whose evolving practices give traditions their life, and it obscures the historical evidence that traditions change over time. Naming this risk early allows the report to keep it in view throughout, and the criteria proposed for WP7&8 are designed to guard against the risk.

Gastro-fundamentalism: an attitude or assumption that treats culinary traditions as fixed, pure, or inviolable, and that risks policing any deviation from a supposed authentic form.

UMIL developed this framework through intensive interdisciplinary collaboration. WP4 brought together philosophers, historians, anthropologists, cognitive scientists, sustainability researchers, and technical specialists across multiple consortium meetings, workshops and dissemination events. This collaborative process, documented in detail in the methodology section, ensures that the conceptual apparatus for typicality remains grounded in empirical observation, expert knowledge and practical feasibility. The framework is the outcome of sustained collective inquiry into real culinary practices, historical trajectories and contemporary challenges.

This collaboration deliberately drew on disciplinary and historical expertise rather than on the direct participation of young adults. This choice reflects the specific aim of D4.2, which is to develop the theoretical and ontological apparatus for operationalising typicality and sustainability, rather than to document how any particular demographic perceives these concepts.

The framework is a conceptual instrument intended to inform platform design. It is not a communication or behaviour-change product aimed at a target audience, and it therefore does not depend on representing young people's views. Youth perspectives nonetheless enter RELISH through a dedicated channel, the youth surveys developed under WP3 for D3.2,¹ whose findings on emerging adults' food practices, perceptions, and future imaginaries are transferred to UMIL so that the frameworks set out here can be tested and aligned against the reality described by younger participants in subsequent work.

The sections that follow present the objectives that guided the research, the methodological approach employed to address them, the empirical data gathered through diverse sources, the findings that emerged from analysis, and the recommendations for future implementation in WP6 and WP7. Together, these components establish an intellectual infrastructure necessary to develop a digital platform that respects cultural diversity, promotes environmental responsibility, and engages younger generations with European culinary heritage.

¹ D3.2 "RELISH Youth Survey and Results Collected for Analysis" can be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/19472257>

2 Objectives

The primary objective for this deliverable is to explicate clear and operational criteria for identifying and evaluating typicality and sustainability within culinary recipes. While straightforward in formulation, developing these criteria encompass multiple conceptual and practical challenges. They required careful consideration before methodological work could proceed effectively.

The objectives outlined here emerged through iterative refinement across early consortium meetings and shaped UMIL's research direction in 2025.

CHALLENGE 1

A conceptual definition for typicality

If recipes are to be classified, represented and recommended through digital platforms, those platforms must operate with definitions that are neither so rigid as to exclude legitimate variation, nor so permissive as to lose analytical utility.

Objective 1: To develop a definition of typicality capable of capturing the relational and dynamic nature of food traditions while providing criteria sufficiently precise for computational implementation.

A conceptual definition for typicality requires distinguishing essential from accidental properties, identifying the dimensions through which typicality manifests, and understanding how communities recognise and articulate what makes recipes and dishes typical.

Our work sought to avoid the trap of essentialism, which treats cultural identity as fixed and unchanging, while also avoiding the opposite error of radical relativism, which would render typicality meaningless by collapsing it into mere subjective preference.

CHALLENGE 2

Historical dimensions of typicality

Early WP4 discussions revealed widespread assumptions that typical foods reflect ancient, unbroken traditions. Preliminary bibliographical research immediately problematised this assumption. Many foods regarded as emblematic of particular regions or nations emerged relatively recently

through processes involving economic development, political institution-building, marketing strategies, and Geographical Indication (GI) certification systems.

Objective 2: To incorporate this historical perspective into the framework, ensuring that the platform would represent typicality as constructed and evolving rather than as primordial essence.

This historical sensibility matters for intellectual accuracy and for cultural politics alike. Narratives of unchanging tradition can become exclusionary tools, marginalising migrant communities, hybrid cuisines, and adaptive practices that do not conform to idealised versions of the past.

CHALLENGE 3

Cognitive and sensory dimensions of typicality

Typicality is not only a matter of ingredients or historical continuity; it also involves recognition patterns, sensory expectations, and embodied knowledge. Communities identify dishes as typical through perceptual cues, flavour memories, and shared evaluative frameworks that are learned socially and reinforced through repeated practice.

Objective 3: To integrate insights from cognitive science and sensory studies into our conceptual model, ensuring that the platform can account for how people actually experience and judge typicality rather than imposing abstract definitions disconnected from lived practice.

Consultation with Institut LYFE's team, whose research focuses on cognitive mechanisms of food categorisation, proved particularly valuable for this dimension.

CHALLENGE 4

Integrating environmental sustainability into typicality framework

Sustainability functions as a constitutive dimension of contemporary culinary practice rather than an optional add-on. Climate change, resource depletion, biodiversity loss, and shifting agricultural zones are transforming the material conditions under which food traditions exist.

Objective 4: To develop criteria for evaluating how recipes might adapt sustainably without losing cultural coherence.

This requires analysing what kinds of substitutions communities accept, under what conditions adaptive changes preserve identity, and how to balance ecological responsibility with respect to cultural meaning. The framework should acknowledge tensions between tradition and environmental necessity while offering pathways for resolution that maintain both cultural value and ecological viability.

CHALLENGE 5

Practical application of criteria

Our analysis cannot remain at the level of philosophical abstraction. It needs to produce operational tools that WP7 and WP8 can translate into database structures, ontological models and user-facing features.

Objective 5: To articulate criteria with sufficient precision and clarity that technical partners can implement them computationally.

This requires close attention to how concepts would function within digital architectures, what kinds of metadata would be required, and how the platform might guide users toward meaningful choices without imposing rigid prescriptions.

CHALLENGE 6

The risk of uniformity

European culinary traditions exhibit extraordinary diversity, shaped by different historical trajectories, ecological contexts, demographic compositions, and cultural values. Any framework applied across this diversity risks flattening difference or imposing dominant patterns as universal norms.

Objective 6: To develop criteria flexible enough to accommodate regional, national and local specificities while maintaining analytical coherence.

This means avoiding one-size-fits-all definitions and remaining attentive to how typicality operates differently across contexts. The framework needs to respect heterogeneity as intrinsic feature rather than as deviation from standard.

CHALLENGE 7

Engaging younger audiences

RELISH targets young people living in Europe who navigate food through digital platforms, global media ecosystems and contemporary environmental consciousness. The criteria developed needs to resonate with their values and experiences rather than merely reflecting older generations' assumptions about tradition.

Objective 7: To frame sustainability, present adaptive possibilities and avoid nostalgic or exclusionary narratives.

The platform should position culinary heritage as living practice open to creative reinterpretation rather than as museum artefact requiring passive preservation.

These challenges and objectives collectively guided the methodological choices, analytical frameworks and empirical inquiries documented in this deliverable. They reflect WP4's commitment to producing work that is philosophically rigorous, historically informed, empirically grounded and practically implementable. The objectives themselves evolved through dialogue across WP4, demonstrating the collaborative and iterative character of the research process. The methodology section that follows explains how these objectives were pursued through specific research activities conducted throughout 2025.

2.1 Discussion on challenges

Defining and operationalising typicality is conceptually demanding. Typicality has multiple layers of meaning and purpose, including historical constructions of food traditions, contemporary environmental pressures, questions of identity and belonging. Additionally, these definitional hurdles usher methodological challenges of designing a digital platform that must respect cultural specificity while promoting sustainable practices.

From the very beginning of WP4, during the first meetings held in March 2025, it became evident that a straightforward definition of typicality would be insufficient for the RELISH project. The concept itself appeared elusive, too rigid when understood as a fixed essence of a dish, yet too vague if conceived simply as whatever communities happen to recognise as "theirs."

We analysed numerous authors' works to confirm that typicality is not an inherent attribute but a **dynamic, historically situated construct**. For example, Magagnoli (2015) shows how “typical products” in Italy were often shaped through economic and political forces rather than handed down through long-standing, continuous traditions. In Magagnoli's account, typicality is something communities construct rather than something they discover, and it tends to emerge in moments of socio-economic transformation rather than through linear historical continuity. Likewise, Ceccarelli, Grandi and Magagnoli (2011) demonstrate how various communities have strategically mobilised references to origin since the Late Middle Ages; these include references to evoke quality, reputation and sensory expectations. This historical development culminated in the 20th century, with fully institutionalised systems of designation that codified typicality for the purposes of trade and marketing. These analyses reveal that typicality has long intertwined with cultural narratives, economic agendas, and political motivations.

From a theoretical perspective, typicality must therefore be treated as a **relational quality** rather than a fixed property of recipes. A dish becomes typical not because of its immutable essence, but because it intersects ingredients, techniques, social practices, symbolic meanings, and historical memory. As Parasecoli (2010) notes in his study of GIs, the typical and the authentic often diverge—something can be typical without being “original,” and another can be historically authentic without corresponding to what communities consider typical today.

The **distinction between authenticity and typicality** is crucial to our project—the RELISH platform must work with categories that communities actually use, without reinforcing essentialist or exclusionary narratives.

Typicality's conceptual complexity is even more pronounced when **sustainability** enters the conversation. Climate change transforms food systems, and biodiversity loss, water scarcity, and shifting agricultural zones have forced European societies to reconsider long-established culinary habits. Dishes central to cultural identity often depend on ingredients whose environmental impacts are high or whose availability is threatened. As Fontefrancesco (2024) explains, increased production of and attention to traditional and local products have intensified in recent decades, but this revival operates within an ecological context that demands new forms of responsibility and adaptive capacity.

Consequently, the question is no longer simply what makes a recipe typical, but **whether such typicality can survive, and how**, under contemporary environmental conditions.

RELISH directly addresses this tension. Young people living in Europe demonstrate a growing desire to reconnect with food heritage as a way of navigating uncertainty,

constructing identity, and building community. The preliminary findings of the RELISH youth survey (D3.2) support these trends. Among emerging-adult respondents, a clear majority reported a preference for home-cooked food and around half expressed a preference for traditional family recipes, while close to half described their own culinary style as traditional and home-based. At the same time, this demographic is increasingly sensitive to environmental concerns and open to substitutions that reduce ecological impact (although the same survey cohort placed environmental concern below price, taste and health).

The coexistence of these impulses, tradition and innovation, memory and sustainability, is where WP4 intervenes. The platform RELISH develops can guide users toward sustainable choices without undermining the cultural value of the recipes that users seek to explore.

A further layer of complexity arises from **demographic and technological transformation**. Migration continues to reshape European culinary landscapes, producing adaptations and hybridised dishes that = become part of local repertoires. For example, Berlin's emblematic street food, the döner kebab, has achieved a status comparative to any historically German dish. Dishes like döner kebab illustrate how typicality is continuously renegotiated.

Similar dynamics were repeatedly highlighted during WP4 internal meetings, especially in March and April 2025, when WP4 members discussed the need to avoid a narrow or exclusionary understanding of cultural belonging. These conversations reinforced that typicality must remain open to change, allowing both historical depth and contemporary evolution to coexist.

Technological innovation further impacts typicality's definitions and use. Lab-grown meats, plant-based analogues, and precision fermentation can impact or challenge long-standing culinary categories. Would a carbonara prepared with lab-grown pancetta still be considered typical of Roman cuisine? What happens to *terroir* when fermentation tanks replicate sensory qualities once tied to specific landscapes?

Narratives of tradition have always adapted to technological change; the key lies in recognising how cultural meaning shifts alongside production methods rather than in policing boundaries artificially.

For these reasons, defining typicality for the RELISH platform requires a methodological framework capable of respecting culinary heritage with openness to adaptation. The framework must avoid essentialism, recognise heterogeneity across communities, and remain sensitive to the environmental realities that shape contemporary food practices. Equally important, it must provide criteria that WP7&8

can translate into computational structures, allowing the platform to represent recipes' complexity in a way that maintains analytical rigour.

The ultimate challenge, therefore, is to determine a definition for typicality that is historically informed, philosophically coherent, empirically grounded, and technologically implementable. It must capture the relational and dynamic nature of food traditions while providing practical guidance for sustainable adaptation.

This deliverable develops such a framework, drawing on historical research, ontological analysis, interdisciplinary dialogue, and the collective insights emerging from WP4's collaborative work throughout 2025.

3 Methodology

The methodological approach developed in WP4 unfolded over collaborative exchanges, informal consultations, conceptual clarifications, workshop testing, and iterative refinement. The approach taken reflects the complexity of the object of study and the need to construct a framework capable of integrating philosophical analysis, historical understanding, interdisciplinary insight, and practical applicability for the platform to be developed in WP7&8.

3.1 Development

The methodology's foundations formed through a series of meetings organised by WP4 held between March and November 2025. These meetings chronologically documented how the group's thinking developed, deepened, and became more precise as the project advanced.

Each meeting contributed specific insights, raised challenges, or introduced new perspectives that shaped the overall methodological orientation. The internal WP4 meetings built and tested conceptual distinction. The joint meetings with other WPs aligned WP4's account of typicality with empirical research and testing conducted elsewhere in the consortium. External expert consultations supplied disciplinary depth on the historical, cognitive, and sustainability dimensions of the framework. Finally, WP4-organised dissemination events served two strategic purposes at once: they exposed the framework to perspectives that sharpened it, and they provided an opportunity to test how the framework and concepts could be communicated to the RELISH target audiences the platform must eventually reach.

The chronologically listed entries below indicate for each activity what elements contributed to the developing framework for typicality and sustainability.

05/03/2025

WP4 meeting

The first formal meeting of WP4 established the basic organisational structure and intellectual orientation for the work ahead. Team members clarified individual responsibilities, coordinated working languages for reports and presentations, and began preliminary discussions about methodological approaches. It became evident that the group needed an approach capable of capturing the tension between tradition and sustainability without reducing either dimension to the other. Early conversations explored how different disciplinary perspectives (philosophical, historical, anthropological, technical) might be integrated into a coherent framework.

The initial exchange established the tone for collaborative inquiry and the need for conceptual precision combined with cultural sensitivity.

10/03/2025

WP4 meeting

Discussions focused on practical questions about data gathering and research design. The team considered how to gather information from both internal consortium sources and external scholarly communities, where to look for relevant literature, whom to contact for interviews or consultations, and what formats reports should take.

These operational considerations shaped decisions about the types of evidence appropriate to addressing questions about typicality. The meeting also began identifying scholars whose expertise could inform our work.

17/03/2025

WP4 meeting with Liselotte Hedegaard (RUC) and Sacramento Roselló-Martínez (Georgetown University)

This joint meeting with colleagues from WP2 and WP3 provided insights into how other WPs were approaching the broader themes of culinary heritage and

memory. Hedegaard and Roselló-Martínez explained their Food Memories² workshop design strategies and introduced the concept of a food memory map, which offered a spatial and narrative dimension to understanding how communities remember and transmit culinary knowledge.

The conversation reinforced the importance of storytelling, identity and belonging as analytical categories that WP4 would need to incorporate into its understanding of typicality. The exchange also clarified interdependencies across WPs, demonstrating how WP4's conceptual work would need to align with empirical research being conducted elsewhere in the consortium.

27/03/2025

WP4 meeting

This meeting addressed theoretical questions that had emerged from early bibliographical research and internal discussions. The team brainstormed about the relationship between typicality and modernity, considering how culinary traditions resist or accommodate standardisation pressures. Conversations explored mechanisms through which communities maintain distinctiveness in the face of globalisation, industrialisation and homogenising market forces.

The meeting also examined connections between typicality and memory, recognising that what makes food typical is often bound up with narrative transmission, generational continuity and the social practices through which memories are preserved and enacted. These reflections deepened the theoretical framework and clarified that typicality requires both structural analysis alone and attention to social and temporal dimensions.

14/04/2025

WP4 meeting

Discussions focused on practical organisation of the research process and conceptual refinement of key ideas. The team established a calendar for informal talks with external scholars and began mapping out how typicality might be represented within digital frameworks.

² See D3.1 "RELISH Food Memories Report" on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/18889651>

Conversations returned repeatedly to the theme of invention and construction, drawing on preliminary readings of historical literature showing that many typical foods arose through relatively recent processes of codification, marketing and GI certification systems. The meeting also addressed the role of advertisement and media representation in shaping public understanding of what counts as typical. By the end of this session, a first outline of the report format began to take shape, providing structure for subsequent research activities.

24/04/2025

WP4 meeting

This meeting clarified the purpose and intended audience of this deliverable. The team discussed how to articulate goals in ways that would be meaningful for consortium partners working on technical implementation. Conversations explored strategies for engaging with people internal to the consortium, who brought diverse disciplinary expertise and practical concerns, and with external scholars, who could provide critical perspective and empirical depth.

The meeting reinforced the importance of producing work that would be rigorous enough for academic scrutiny and accessible enough for interdisciplinary collaboration and public communication.

28/04/2025

WP4 meeting with Liselotte Hedegaard (RUC) and Sacramento Roselló-Martínez (Georgetown University)

A second joint meeting with WP2 and WP3 colleagues focused on preparing the Food Memories workshop design (WP3). Hedegaard and Roselló-Martínez shared a first draft of the workshop design and explained how they planned to address questions about the relationship between identity, belonging, and storytelling.

This exchange helped WP4 understand how narrative dimensions of culinary practice might be operationalised in research settings, and how communities represent connections between food and identity through storytelling practices. The insights gained from this conversation influenced later decisions about how to represent narrative typicality within WP4's framework.

23/05/2025

WP4 meeting

This meeting reported progress on D4.2. Members reflected on audience considerations and refined understandings of the relationship between typicality and recipes. The team revisited earlier ideas about report format and structure, incorporating insights from previous meetings and ongoing bibliographical research.

Conversations addressed how to present complex philosophical arguments in ways that would be accessible to readers without specialist training.

25 - 27/06/2025

Braga International Conference

Participation in the “Food Injustice” panel at Braga International academic conference in Portugal provided exposure to critical perspectives on food systems, environmental ethics, and social justice. Presentations addressed issues related to food waste, ecological responsibility, and ethical dimensions of production and consumption.

The conference enriched WP4’s understanding of sustainability by highlighting how environmental concerns intersect with questions of justice, equity and power. Insights from these discussions influenced later decisions about how to frame sustainability within the RELISH platform, ensuring that the platform would treat environmental criteria as ethical commitments with social implications that go beyond purely technical constraints.

14/07/2025 | 21/07/2025

WP4 meetings

These two meetings focused on finalising the design and content of a Google Form survey that would be distributed to key consortium members. The survey aimed to gather qualitative insights about how different disciplinary communities understand typicality, what criteria they consider relevant, and what challenges they encounter when working with concepts of tradition, authenticity, and sustainability.

The meetings refined question wording, anticipated potential ambiguities, and ensured that the survey would elicit responses useful for the conceptual development of the framework.

25/09/2025

Meeting with Jérémie Lafraire (EPHE, École Pratique des Hautes Études)

We consulted cognitive scientist Jérémie Lafraire to understand how typicality operates as a psychological and perceptual phenomenon. Lafraire's research focuses on categorisation processes, prototypicality, and cognitive mechanisms through which individuals recognise and evaluate foods. During the meeting, Lafraire explained how cognitive prototypes function differently from philosophical essences, operating through family resemblance structures and graded membership rather than strict definitional boundaries. He discussed how typicality judgments involve both *perceptual recognition*—based on sensory cues like flavour, aroma and appearance—and *cultural learning*—the way individuals acquire expectations about what should count as typical through socialisation and repeated exposure.

Lafraire also introduced the concept of *cognitive flexibility*, explaining that individuals vary in how rigidly or loosely they apply categorical boundaries, such as typicality. Some people demonstrate conservative tendencies and maintain strict criteria for what counts as authentic or typical, while others exhibit greater openness to variation and adaptation.

Variability in cognitive flexibility impacts how communities respond to sustainable substitutions, since those with more flexible cognitive frameworks may accept ingredient changes more readily, while those with rigid prototypes may perceive such changes as threatening to identity. Lafraire emphasised that these cognitive tendencies interact with cultural contexts, personal experiences, and value system. This implied that typicality dimensions can be neither purely cognitive nor purely cultural. Typicality should be understood as emerging through their interaction.

We also discussed comparative dimensions of typicality. Lafraire noted that judgments about what is typical often involve implicit or explicit comparisons across contexts: *e.g.*, urban versus rural environments, different age cohorts, regional variations and national boundaries. What counts as typical in one setting may be perceived as atypical in another. These contextual variations must be accounted for in any framework attempting to operationalise typicality. He suggested that data collection efforts should seek to gather not

only to what people identify as typical, but also to the implicit comparisons they make, the criteria they use to justify their judgments, and the degree of flexibility they demonstrate when evaluating variants.

Finally, Lafraire stressed measuring rigidity and conservatism when studying typicality. Understanding whether communities or individuals are more or less open to change provides crucial information for designing sustainable interventions. If the platform can identify factors that predict openness to sustainable substitutions, such as age, urban versus rural location, previous exposure to diverse cuisines, or explicit environmental values, we can tailor recommendations to respect cognitive and cultural tendencies, while encouraging adaptation when appropriate.

These insights reinforced WP4's commitment to developing frameworks that are conceptually grounded and empirically sensitive to how people actually think about and experience food.

13/10/2025

WP4 meeting

This meeting provided preparation updates for WP5's methodological framework workshop, "Recipes and Gastronomy as Cultural Heritage: Meaning, Methodology, and Media," scheduled for later in October 2025 at the University of Gastronomic Sciences, Pollenzo (UNISG). The team discussed how the workshop would provide opportunities to test emerging ideas about typicality and sustainability with external participants and attending RELISH members.

Early discussions about report structure also began during this meeting, as the team anticipated needing to synthesise findings from diverse sources into a coherent deliverable.

22-24/10/2025

Methodological Framework Workshop³ at UNISG (Pollenzo)

The three-day workshop at UNISG in Pollenzo provided an opportunity for attending RELISH consortium members to exchange updates on progress

³ A full breakdown of workshop activities can be found in D5.1, "Report on Methodological Framework Workshop," on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/20967900>

across different WPs in-person. After the workshop, WP4 received clearer instructions about the format for deliverables.

30/10/2025

WP4 meeting

Following the Pollenzo workshop, the team reconvened to revise the methodological section of the deliverable based on insights gained. The meeting focused particularly on strengthening the methodology by documenting the iterative process through which concepts had been developed, refined and tested. Discussions emphasised how to present the methodology as a collaborative and adaptive process responsive to empirical realities and disciplinary diversity.

20/11/2025

Discussion with Giorgio Ubbiali (University of Milan)

This informal consultation with food ontology researcher Giorgio Ubbiali provided methodological perspectives for studying sustainability in food systems. Ubbiali, whose research focusses on developing ontologies for food systems sustainability, shared insights about his research process, the challenges of operationalising sustainability concepts, and strategies for integrating diverse stakeholder perspectives into formal frameworks. Ubbiali's work on participatory ontology design and meta-frameworks for food systems sustainability offered methodological parallels to WP4's own approach combining philosophical rigour with empirical sensitivity and technical implementation.

04/2025 - 11/2025

Dissemination through Culinary Mind (UMIL)

Culinary Mind: The Centre for Philosophy of Food at the University of Milan was the main outreach arm of WP4 throughout 2025. The Centre promotes the philosophical study of food and convenes academics, students, and the wider public around culinary culture, ethics and sustainability.

For RELISH, Culinary Mind functioned strategically in three connected ways: 1) It gave the project a standing venue to present its work to non-consortium

audiences; 2) It brought leading external scholars into direct dialogue with WP4 at moments when the framework was still taking shape; and 3) It acted as a testing ground where the report's claims about typicality and sustainability met expert and public scrutiny before reaching the platform stage.

Between April and November 2025, Culinary Mind hosted a continuous programme of events hosting Nicola Perullo (UNISG), Laurette Dube (McGill University), Jeroen Struben (EM Lyon), Giancarlo Guizzardi (University of Twente), and Kwabena Edusei (Hamilton College), over four thematic symposia. These contributors gave WP4 access to philosophy of food, formal ontology, decolonial food studies, food-system transformation, food and tourism, microbiome and fermentation, food and media, and consumer food experience. This engagement matters for D4.2 because it grounds the framework in dialogue rather than in solitary analysis, as well as equips the project with the audiences and channels through which the RELISH platform will eventually reach the target audiences and emerging adults for which the project is designed.

Through this sequence of meetings, dissemination events, workshops, and consultations, the methodological orientation crystallised into a cohesive, interdisciplinary framework that brings conceptual clarity and practical relevance to future applications. Throughout 2025, we developed the methodology organically through sustained dialogue, iterative refinement, and careful attention to the challenges posed by operationalising typicality and sustainability for digital platforms.

3.2 Literature review

A review of relevant literature supported the preliminary framework and criteria for operationalising typicality and sustainability. Since both concepts are multidimensional concepts, the literature review incorporated multiple perspectives from food history, philosophy, environmental science, anthropology, marketing, and sensory studies.

Historical literature was particularly influential. Scholars such as Ceccarelli, Grandi, and Magagnoli (2011) demonstrate that many foods regarded today as “traditional” or “typical” arose from relatively recent economic, political, or market-driven developments. Their studies reveal that the history of typicality is inseparable from institutionalisation: *e.g.*, GIs, branding and the management of origin-linked reputations. These institutional processes intensified in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Historical review ensured that our methodology did not fall into the trap of essentialising typicality.

Anthropological and sociological works enriched this understanding. The reviewed studies emphasise the social construction of taste and the relational nature of food practices. Research by Fontefrancesco (2020, 2024)—on food festivals and local development, as well as on the construction of typicality in community products, together with his analysis on how tradition interacts with sustainability—foregrounds the tensions communities face when attempting to preserve culinary identity under ecological constraints. Sensory studies, including the work of Maitre, Symoneaux, Jourjon and Mehinagic (2010) on the sensory typicality of wines, provided empirical frameworks for examining how communities recognise and define typicality. These studies highlight that typicality is both historically and culturally mediated, and an embodied, sensory practice linked to recognition patterns and shared expectations.

Philosophical literature offered conceptual tools for addressing identity persistence, essential and accidental properties, and the ontological status of recipes. This included foundational texts on food and recipe ontology by Borghini (2015, 2024) and Borghini and Engisch (2022), analyses of recipes as cultural and computational objects (Borghini, Piras and Bacchini 2020), and reflections on the nature of authenticity drawn from this body of work. These philosophical resources provided frameworks for thinking systematically about what makes a recipe the kind of entity that can sustain changes without losing its identity, and how to distinguish between modifications that preserve recognisability and those that transform dishes into something else entirely.

Environmental sustainability literature—particularly the work of Piso, Werkheiser, Noll and Leshko (2016) on multidimensional frameworks for the values that sustainable agriculture works to sustain—foregrounds the need to connect typicality with resource use, environmental pressures, and ethical frameworks related to ecological responsibility. Piso et al.'s emphasis on moving beyond narrow, carbon-focused metrics toward holistic assessments encompassing biodiversity, water use, soil health, social equity, and cultural value aligns with RELISH's aim to develop a comprehensive understanding of recipes as cultural artefacts that are also embedded elements of ecological and social systems.

Food studies literature addressing GIs and Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) certification systems—particularly Fabio Parasecoli's research (2010, 2022) examining the gender dimensions and political implications of origin labelling—demonstrates how typicality becomes codified in legal and institutional frameworks. Parasecoli's concept of *gastronativism*, which describes how stakeholders mobilise food narratives for identity politics and boundary-making, offers a critical perspective on the risks

inherent in framing culinary heritage in essentialist terms. Parasecoli's work underlines why RELISH should avoid reinforcing exclusionary narratives while still providing meaningful criteria for recognising and valuing cultural specificity.

Cognitive sciences literature—through our consultation with the cognitive scientist Jérémie Lafraire (EPHE)—established that typicality works through forms of graded membership rather than through strict definitional boundaries. Graded membership means that a dish belongs to a culinary category by degrees, counting as a more or a less central example rather than solely qualifying or failing to qualify. Goldberg, Hannan and Kovács (2016) reinforce this view from **sociology**, since they treat typicality as the degree to which an object conforms to a category's prototype rather than as a fixed essence. This account shapes the framework's emphasis on relational patterns rather than fixed essences.

Together, these bibliographical sources provide the theoretical resources for developing our methodological framework, since they reveal typicality as a historically dynamic, socially negotiated, and often contested category, as well as sustainability as a moral, environmental and socio-political imperative deeply entangled with food practices. By combining insights from these diverse disciplines, the literature review supports a methodology that is grounded in established scholarship and adaptable to the practical needs of a digital platform.

A visual representation of this review can be found in **Figure 1**. The figure presents typicality as a relational integrity and sustainability as adaptive resilience, identifying three key bridging avenues: functional substitution, cognitive prototypicality, and sensory and narrative continuity. The three avenues enable culinary traditions to evolve while remaining culturally recognisable. The typicality framework highlights how adaptation can support cultural continuity and environmental responsibility without reducing traditions to fixed or essentialised terms.

1 BEYOND FIXED TRADITION: BRIDGING TYPICALITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

A dynamic approach to culinary heritage

Figure 1: Conceptual framework illustration the relationship between culinary typicality and environmental sustainability.

3.3 Ontological analysis

Ontological analysis addresses what makes a recipe the kind of entity that can sustain changes without losing its identity. This analysis seeks to distinguish between **essential** and **accidental properties** of recipes, namely which ingredients, techniques or contextual features are necessary for a dish to be recognised as what it is, and which elements may vary without compromising typicality. Through this lens, typicality emerges as a pattern of relations that can be preserved across changes.

The ontological work was refined through numerous internal discussions throughout April and May 2025. The team considered how recipes function as relational entities embedded within social rituals and shaped by historical circumstances. Rather than treating recipes as isolated objects, the analysis situated them within networks of practices, meanings and expectations.

During meetings on April 14th and 24th, the team explored how advertisement, GIs, and invented traditions influence public understanding of typicality. Conversations on May 23rd reinforced the need for an ontological approach sensitive to historical evolution and cultural significance.

The subsequent consultations with Giovanni Ceccarelli (University of Milan) and Stefano Magagnoli (University of Parma) in late May 2025 provided historical depth to the conceptual distinctions drawn, further grounding the ontological model in real cases. Ceccarelli offered detailed historical accounts of how origin designations emerged in medieval and early modern Europe. He demonstrated how references to place became tied to quality expectations and market value long before modern GI systems were established. Magagnoli provided concrete examples of industrial processes and political institutions that shaped foods now regarded as quintessentially traditional, demonstrating that the apparent naturalness of typicality often masks complex histories of construction and codification.

An ontological philosophical approach ensures conceptual consistency while remaining attentive to cultural nuance. The ontological framework developed through these discussions treats recipes as maintaining identity through relational integrity, the preservation of recognisable patterns across multiple dimensions, including ingredients, techniques, sensory profiles, social contexts, and narrative associations. A relational approach allows for variation and adaptation. It also provides criteria for judging when changes have become so extensive that the dish can no longer be recognised as the same entity.

3.4 Informal consultations

The methodology incorporated direct engagement with scholars whose expertise could deepen the conceptual framework. Several informal consultations provided insights that literature review alone could not offer.

20/05/2025

Giovanni Ceccarelli (University of Milan)

The consultation with historian Giovanni Ceccarelli focused on the historical emergence of typical foods and the evolution of origin-linked designations in European culinary traditions.

Ceccarelli explained how medieval merchants and producers began associating place names with quality expectations, creating early forms of geographical indications that would later be formalised through legal and

institutional mechanisms. He discussed specific cases, including the development of reputation systems for wines, cheeses, and cured meats, showing how economic interests, political authority, and cultural narratives converged to construct typicality as a marketable attribute. Ceccarelli also discussed the role of guilds, municipal regulations, and trade protections in codifying production standards that came to be understood as traditional.

This consultation provided concrete historical examples that grounded the theoretical framework in documented practices, reinforcing the understanding that typicality is constructed through social, economic, and political processes, rather than discovered as inherent property.

26/05/2025

Stefano Magagnoli (University of Parma)

The consultation with historian Stefano Magagnoli examined the invention of tradition and the socio-economic forces shaping iconic foods in modern Italy.

Magagnoli drew on his research into Parmigiano-Reggiano cheese, explaining how this product—now emblematic of Italian culinary tradition—was substantially transformed through industrial processes, standardisation efforts, and marketing campaigns in the 19th and 20th centuries. He discussed how narratives of timeless tradition were deliberately constructed to support commercial interests and regional identities. These narratives often obscure the historical contingency and recent origins of supposedly ancient practices. Magagnoli also reflected on the role of GIs in fixing typicality through legal definitions, noting both their value in protecting producer communities and their tendency to ossify practices that had historically been more fluid.

The consultation reinforced the framework's emphasis on understanding typicality as dynamic and constructed, while also highlighting tensions between preservation and adaptation that remain unresolved in contemporary food politics.

These consultations enriched the methodology by grounding theoretical insights in expert knowledge and practical experience. They demonstrated the value of direct dialogue with scholars working on related questions, allowing WP4 to refine concepts, test assumptions, and incorporate disciplinary perspectives that might otherwise have been overlooked or misunderstood.

3.5 Short survey design and distribution

An internal survey—developed in July 2025 and refined through two dedicated meetings on July 14th and 21st—broadened the qualitative components of the methodology. The survey was not intended to be statistically representative. We used it to capture **conceptual divergences and convergences** among scholars from within the consortium working on topics related to typicality and sustainability.

The survey invited respondents to reflect on how typicality operates within their respective fields, what criteria they consider relevant for identifying typical foods, what theoretical and practical challenges they encounter, and what sources they regard as foundational for understanding typicality.

The survey instrument consisted of nine questions addressing multiple dimensions:

- Polysemy and context-dependence of typicality
- Criteria determining what counts as typical
- Theoretical challenges in conceptualising typicality
- Ethical concerns related to typical foods
- Practical obstacles to research
- Keywords defining typicality

Questions were deliberately open-ended to allow respondents freedom to articulate their perspectives in their own terms rather than selecting from predetermined categories.

The three consortium members who provided substantive responses are all historians, though they work across distinct historical specialisms. Simone Cinotto (UNISG) is a historian of modern and contemporary history whose work centres on Italian-American foodways, migration and the politics of taste. Daniel Bender (UoT) is a cultural historian of food, working on global and transnational food history. Regina Sexton (UCC) is a food and culinary historian of Ireland whose recent work also draws on social science theory and critical food studies.

Their shared disciplinary background is a strength, since historical expertise speaks directly to the constructed character of typicality, but it also means these responses represent one disciplinary subgroup within RELISH rather than the full range of perspectives held across the consortium (which also includes philosophers, cognitive scientists, sustainability researchers and technical partners). We read the survey results with that limitation in mind.

The three responses are summarised as follows:

09/03/2025

Simone Cinotto (UNISG)

An historian of Italian–American foodways, Cinotto emphasised the role of narratives in constructing typicality. He highlighted how different authorities, governmental, commercial, media, and culinary practices produce competing narratives about what counts as typical, and how these narratives become dominant and powerful through processes described through political theorist and philosopher Antonio Gramsci’s concept of *cultural hegemony* and national-popular consensus.

Cinotto also flagged the politicisation and commodification of typicality as key challenges, noting that certain groups instrumentalise food for identity politics and market purposes.

24/10/2025

Daniel Bender (UoT)

An historian of food and empire, Bender contributed a detailed response focused on wine, a domain where typicality is culturally significant and legally defined. Bender described how typicality in wine involves both organoleptic criteria tested by official tasting committees, and structural characteristics including acidity, phenolic composition, colour, and aroma profiles. He identified climate change as a major transformational force affecting wine typicality, noting how shifting temperature patterns and weather extremes alter the sensory characteristics of wines from established regions. His historical lens framed these sensory shifts as part of a longer story about how legal and commercial categories for typicality are made and remade over time.

Bender also discussed the ways that formal tasting education depends on notions of typicality tied to GIs, raising challenges about how climate-driven changes may necessitate revisions to PDO regulations. His response included specific academic references addressing climate impacts on wine composition and typicality.

30/10/2025

Regina Sexton

A food and culinary historian of Ireland, Sexton provided extensive reflection on the Irish context, emphasising the relevance of polysemy given Ireland's complex demographic profile shaped by class hierarchies and colonial legacies. She noted how globalisation has flattened food cultures in the Global North since the mid-20th century, producing greater homogenisation while simultaneously generating new forms of temporal, spatial, demographic and religious differentiation.

Sexton identified several criteria as essential for understanding Irish food typicality: continuity of practice and tradition; sociologist Pierre Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* (conscious and subconscious practices and comportment); links to social norms and festive or religious events; and collectively constructed taste preferences.

Sexton also discussed challenges specific to Irish food history, including the marginalisation of food studies within historical disciplines, the legacy of male-dominated historiography that dismissed food as trivial, and the persistence of unchallenged culinary myths. Her response included an extensive bibliography spanning sociology, history, anthropology, and cultural studies.

Each respondent provided rich qualitative insights reflecting different regional contexts and thematic specialisms within food history. Even among historians, typicality is understood through different emphases. Cinotto stressed narrative construction, political contestation, and commodification; Bender foregrounded legal and sensory definitions of typicality and their vulnerability to climate change; and Sexton emphasised *habitus*, continuity of practice, and the embeddedness of food within social rituals and festive cycles.

These divergences within a single discipline reinforced the need for a flexible and pluralistic framework that accommodates varied perspectives while maintaining analytical coherence.

3.6 Integrated methodological framework

By October 2025, the methodology integrated the previous activities into a shared framework. The framework treats recipes as relational entities defined by patterns of ingredients, techniques, social practices, and symbolic meanings. It recognises that

typicality arises historically through repeated practice, communal recognition, and narrative circulation, and that sustainability must be integrated as a constitutive dimension of typicality rather than as an external limitation.

The framework is articulated around three axes:

1. **The ontological structure of recipes:** providing criteria for identifying essential properties and evaluating identity persistence across variation
2. **The historical and social evolution of typicality:** revealing how cultural meaning is formed and transformed through economic, political, and narrative processes
3. **The environmental dimension:** acknowledging that ecological pressures shape both availability and acceptability of ingredients and practices

This integrated approach ensures that the platform developed in WP7&8 will be able to represent recipes dynamically and model historical continuity and sustainable adaptation in a meaningful and culturally sensitive way.

The methodology has limitations. The informal consultations and survey responses, while insightful, reflect a limited sample size and cannot capture the full diversity of European culinary traditions. The literature review necessarily omits many regional perspectives and language-specific sources. Workshop activities offered valuable testing environments but involved only a subset of stakeholders.

Nonetheless, these limitations are appropriate to the scope of D4.2, whose purpose is to establish the conceptual and methodological foundations for further technical development and empirical refinement in subsequent phases of the project.

3.7 Processing and presenting data

Developing the methodological framework in WP4 required systematically organising the diverse materials gathered throughout 2025. This process involved assembling a coherent body of evidence capable of supporting the conceptual distinctions and analytical criteria presented in this report.

Because typicality is not a phenomenon that can be isolated in laboratory conditions, the data underlying this deliverable comes from a wide array of sources, including historical literature, philosophical analysis, consultation with scholars, informal conversations within the consortium, workshops, and the responses gathered through a digital survey designed specifically for D4.2.

Each source contributed distinct and useful elements for conceptually defining and operationalising typicality and sustainability. The final framework reflects the variety of inputs.

The first layer of data stems from the literature review. Historical analyses provided documented evidence that typicality is historically contingent, constructed through economic and political processes, and often codified through GI systems. Anthropological and sociological works enriched this historical base by offering ethnographic insights into how communities negotiate meaning through food. Sensory science studies provided empirical structures for understanding the perceptual recognition of typicality. Philosophical literature contributed conceptual clarity regarding identity conditions and the structure of cultural objects. Environmental sustainability literature expanded the framework by foregrounding ecological dimensions, ethical considerations, and the interaction between food practices and broader ecological systems. This research foundation forms the backbone of the analytical lens through which all additional data was interpreted.

Complementing the literature were the informal consultations carried out in May 2025. Conversations with Giovanni Ceccarelli and Stefano Magagnoli offered concrete historical examples of how typical foods emerge, circulate and transform. Their research confirmed many of the patterns observed in the literature but added nuance, contextual detail, and scholarly experience that the written record alone could not provide. Ceccarelli's account of medieval origin designations and Magagnoli's analysis of industrial transformation in modern Italian food production provided specific cases that grounded abstract concepts in documented historical realities.

Informal consultations with other scholars added further layers of insight. The meeting with Jérémie Lafraire introduced cognitive and perceptual dimensions, explaining how individuals categorise and recognise foods through prototype structures and how cognitive flexibility influences openness to variation and adaptation. Lafraire's emphasis on comparative categorisation, measures of rigidity, and the interaction between individual cognition and cultural context enriched the framework's understanding of how typicality operates as a psychological phenomenon embedded within social learning. Similarly, discussions with Giorgio Ubbiali about sustainability methodologies provided parallel perspectives on how to operationalise complex normative concepts in formal frameworks, reinforcing the value of participatory approaches and iterative refinement.

The survey conducted in July 2025 provided yet another layer of data. Although not statistically representative, the three substantive responses revealed conceptual tendencies among participants from the same discipline, since all three respondents are historians of food working in different regional and thematic areas. Cinotto emphasised narrative construction, political contestation, and commodification.

Bender foregrounded the legal and sensory criteria that define wine typicality and their vulnerability to environmental change, while Sexton emphasised practice, *habitus*, continuity and the embeddedness of food within social rituals and festive cycles. These patterns were treated as indicators of how historians working in different areas understand typicality. The survey thus served as a conceptual diagnostic, revealing areas of convergence and divergence that the final framework needed to accommodate.

Finally, the broader sequence of consortium meetings yielded substantial qualitative data. These meetings, documented chronologically in the methodology section, were iterative checkpoints for the development of concepts, allowing the team to refine definitions, test distinctions, and integrate insights emerging from multiple WPs. The evolution of thinking across these meetings—from initial uncertainty about how to define typicality to the articulation of a multi-dimensional relational framework—demonstrates the collaborative and emergent character of conceptual development within WP4.

Table 1 below synthesises the main data sources used in this deliverable, their nature, and their contribution to the operationalisation of typicality and sustainability.

Table 1: Literature review and data sources.

SOURCE TYPE	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	PERIOD / DATE	CONTRIBUTION TO WP4
Bibliographical Literature	Historical analyses (Magagnoli, Ceccarelli, Grandi), anthropological texts (Fontefrancesco), sensory studies (Maitre), sustainability frameworks (Noll, Werkheiser), philosophical work on ontology and authenticity (Borghini, Parasecoli)	2000–2024	Provided conceptual vocabulary; historical cases; models of sensory typicality; frameworks for sustainability; ontological tools for analysing recipe identity
Consultation	Informal consultation with Giovanni Ceccarelli and Stefano Magagnoli	20/05/2025; 26/05/2025	Offered historical depth, expert interpretations of typicality, examples of constructed traditions, insights into the economic and social emergence of iconic foods
Informal Consultations	Cognitive science insights (Lafraire), sustainability methodology (Ubbiali), internal discussions with consortium scholars	25/09/2025; 20/11/2025	Added nuance to categorisation processes, cognitive flexibility, sustainability criteria, and philosophical positioning of WP4

SOURCE TYPE	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	PERIOD / DATE	CONTRIBUTION TO WP4
Survey Responses	Google Form distributed to consortium members	July 2025 (responses received September–October 2025)	Mapped disciplinary divergences, revealed conceptual tendencies, informed the pluralistic orientation of the final framework
Internal Meetings	WP4 meetings; joint meetings with WP2 & WP3; internal planning sessions	March–November 2025 (12 documented meetings)	Provided chronological development of the methodology, convergence of ideas, and iterative refinement of conceptual distinctions
Workshops	Methodological Framework Workshop in UNISG (Pollenzo)	22–24/10/2025	Gathered feedback on deliverable format, identified areas requiring further refinement
External Academic Events	Braga International Conference (Food Injustice panel); Culinary Mind symposia on Tourism, Microbiome, Media, Philosophy	25–27/06/2025; September–November 2025	Expanded sustainability dimension; contributed to ethical and ecological understanding of food systems; enriched theoretical perspectives

These materials form a coherent and multi-layered evidentiary base. Through comparing literature with expert insight, aligning survey responses with historical cases, and verifying theoretical distinctions through practical workshop analysis, the team was able to construct a framework that is philosophically rigorous and attuned to the complexities and varieties of real-world culinary practices.

4 Discussion

The findings that emerged from WP4 display a recurring tension between continuity and adaptation, confirming that typicality is shaped by both historical memory and contemporary constraints. Through the combination of bibliographical research, consultation, survey responses, and workshop analysis, it became evident that typicality cannot be reduced to a single dimension. It is a layered concept intersecting cultural identity, sensory recognition, narrative transmission, and ecological feasibility. This complexity reflects the nature of culinary practices, which have

always evolved through interactions between people, environments, and technologies.

4.1 Typicality themes

4.1.1 *Origins and designations*

Origin designations are the most concrete form in which typicality reaches the platform, and tracing how they come into being and evolve demonstrates how typicality behaves. In an informal consultation, the historian Giovanni Ceccarelli described a sequence that recurs across cases. Producers' guilds in early-modern Europe operated under a tacit agreement with the political power and used it to regulate production, set rules, and raise barriers against outside producers, which tied a product to a place long before formal certification existed. Producers later adopted a denomination because it already carried a reputation in distant markets, as happened with the name Parmesan in England and the United States, which gave the local Parmigiano denomination commercial value and prompted its formalisation. Precise legal regulation arrived much later, well into the 19th century. Magagnoli's analysis of Parmigiano-Reggiano shows what happens after codification, namely that industrial transformation and marketing narratives layer an aura of timeless tradition onto the comparatively recent legal arrangement.

Across these stages, typicality is not a property the designation discovers and protects. It is something the designation gradually becomes.

This pattern has direct implications for typicality framework. Because designations are themselves the outcome of revision and continue to be revised, the platform should not treat them as the final word on what a recipe must contain, and it should make their evolutionary character visible by surfacing the ingredients and techniques that have moved in and out of a tradition over time. Sustainable substitutions then appear as a continuation of the same process through which designations have always developed, rather than as a departure. This stance disciplines the framework against essentialist readings of origin designations and gives WP7&8 a principled basis for modelling typicality as a living claim that communities revise.

4.1.2 *Cognitive and sensory perceptions*

A second set of findings concerns **the cognitive and sensory dimensions** of typicality, and these too carry implications for platform design. Our consultation with the cognitive scientist Jérémie Lafraire established that typicality functions as a living evaluative process rather than as a static descriptive label, working through graded membership and family resemblance rather than through strict definitional

boundaries. The practical consequence is that individuals vary in how rigidly or flexibly they apply categorical criteria, and that this variation predicts how they respond to change. Those who hold rigid prototypes are likely to perceive ingredient substitutions as threats to identity, while those with more flexible prototypes accept variation more readily. If the platform can identify the factors that predict openness to adaptation, such as age, urban or rural location, prior exposure to diverse cuisines or explicit environmental values, it can tailor recommendations in ways that respect cognitive and cultural tendencies while still encouraging sustainable change. Lafraire also stressed that typicality judgments involve implicit comparisons across contexts, since what counts as typical in one setting may be perceived as atypical in another.

The platform should therefore record not only what users identify as typical but also the comparisons they draw and the criteria they invoke.

4.1.3 Social narratives

A third dimension concerns the social and narrative character of typicality. Meetings with colleagues from WP3 and WP5 early in the year drew attention to the importance of memory, storytelling, and belonging. These discussions resonated strongly with anthropological literature showing that recipes carry meanings that exceed their material composition. Survey respondents highlighted context, festivities, family gatherings, and local rituals as essential markers of typicality, and Regina Sexton's response emphasised continuity of practice, *habitus*, conscious and subconscious behaviours, and linkages to social norms and festive calendars.

Taken together, these findings indicate that RELISH cannot operationalise typicality through ingredients or techniques alone. They depend on social scripts, namely when and how recipes are prepared, who prepares them, and what they symbolise within communities. The digital infrastructure must therefore accommodate metadata about contexts of consumption, ritual significance, seasonal variations, and the stories communities narrate about their food.

4.2 Sustainability themes

4.2.1 Environment and social justice

The sustainability dimension brought a further layer of complexity. Scholarly sources on sustainability emphasise that ecological pressures, including climate change, water scarcity, soil degradation and biodiversity loss, transform the conditions under which culinary traditions can be maintained, and that environmental considerations cannot be reduced to carbon metrics but must encompass social equity, cultural value, biodiversity protection, and long-term ecological viability.

Participation in the Braga panel on food injustice confirmed this insight from an ethical and systemic perspective. Conference discussions highlighted how environmental harms and benefits are distributed unequally across populations, with marginalised communities often bearing disproportionate costs of industrial food systems while having limited access to sustainable alternatives.

Sustainability must therefore be framed not only as environmental protection but also as social justice.

4.2.2 Sustainable substitutions

Consultations and workshop discussions revealed an emerging consensus that communities increasingly accept sustainable substitutions even where they continue to value continuity. Daniel Bender's survey response on wine typicality illustrated the tension clearly. Climate change is altering the organoleptic characteristics of wines from established regions, raising questions about whether protected designation of origin regulations will need revision to accommodate environmental realities. Bender noted that formal tasting education depends heavily on notions of typicality tied to GIs, which creates potential conflicts between regulatory definitions and sensory realities as climates shift. Adaptation patterns appeared across domains. Communities recognise that some ingredients may become unavailable or ecologically unsustainable, but they resist changes that seem to undermine cultural identity or ignore their evaluative frameworks.

The framework must therefore provide criteria for judging when substitutions preserve sufficient relational integrity to maintain typicality and when they cross thresholds that render dishes unrecognisable.

4.2.3 Preferences and practices

Survey responses and meeting discussions suggested that communities evaluate sustainable substitutions through implicit normative criteria. Substitutions are more likely to be accepted when they preserve the way a dish is made, the way it is recognised by the senses, or the story it tells, and when these conditions are met, innovations are often welcomed. When they are not, resistance emerges.

Typicality and sustainability are therefore not opposing forces. They can align when approached with sensitivity to cultural context. Regina Sexton's emphasis on *habitus* and practice proved particularly relevant here. Drawing on Pierre Bourdieu's concept of *habitus*, Sexton explained how food preferences and practices become embodied through socialisation, creating dispositions that feel natural and inevitable even though they are culturally constructed.

This suggests that sustainable adaptation requires technical substitutions together with gradual shifts in *habitus*, achieved through positive experiences with adapted recipes, narrative reframing that maintains cultural continuity, and social validation from trusted community members.

4.3 Essentialism as cross-cutting theme

A cross-cutting theme emerged across all sources, namely the risk of essentialism. If typicality is defined too narrowly, it becomes exclusionary, ignores historical change and fails to account for contemporary realities. If it is defined too broadly, it loses analytical utility and risks endorsing forms of typicality that the project has good reasons to exclude, including the gastro-nativist and exclusionary uses that Parasecoli describes.

The framework therefore needs to be responsive but selective. It must adapt to historical evidence and to changing conditions, but it must also rule out readings of typicality that turn food traditions into instruments of exclusion.

The structured criteria the framework proposes do this work by holding together multiple dimensions at once: historical continuity, sensory recognition, the way a dish is made, narrative significance, contextual embeddedness, and cultural acceptability. A claim of typicality has to register across several of these dimensions to count, which is what makes the framework selective rather than infinitely permissive.

In the context of sustainability, this structured selectivity becomes operational. Ecological pressures, changing climates, declining availability of certain ingredients, and the environmental cost of animal-based products already reshape what communities perceive as viable or desirable. The question is no longer whether traditions will change, but how, and within what frameworks of meaning. When substitutions maintain how a dish is made, how it is recognised by the senses, or the story it tells, communities tend to accept them as legitimate adaptations rather than as threats to tradition.

Representing typicality in this responsive and selective way is what the digital platform stands to add. A static database can record that a dish is “typical of” a region; it cannot show why, or what could change without that claim breaking. A dynamic representation can. It lets users see which features of a recipe carry the weight of typicality and which are incidental, why a particular substitution preserves the dish and why another would not, and how the tradition itself has already shifted across time.

For users, this reframes the experience of working with a typical recipe. Instead of receiving an unexplained verdict on whether a dish counts as authentic, they see the reasoning, and they encounter sustainable adaptation as an extension of the tradition rather than as a violation of it. This is what the framework offers the consortium, and it forms the basis for the operational criteria and conceptual tools that will support the development of the RELISH platform in the next stages of the project.

A visual representation of this discussion can be found in **Figure 2**. The figure outlines a stepwise process for identifying core recipe features, assessing sustainability pressures, implementing substitutions, and evaluating continuity across sensory, procedural, narrative, and community dimensions. Using the example of a traditional ragù adapted through alternative ingredients, the framework demonstrates how sustainable modifications can preserve recipe identity while reducing environmental impact.

Figure 2: Operational framework for evaluating and adapting culinary recipes within the RELISH platform.

5 Future Directions and Recommendations

The findings of WP4 point toward several directions and recommendations for the next phases of the RELISH project. As WP7&8 begin transforming these conceptual criteria into computational structures and user-oriented interfaces, the question becomes how to preserve the analytical richness of typicality while ensuring that the platform remains accessible, adaptive and culturally sensitive.

Our recommendations (discussed further below) are as follows:

1. Avoid applying typicality as a rigid, “gastro-fundamentalist” tool
2. Share and apply conceptual frameworks using accessible, user-friendly digital tools for young people living in Europe
3. Integrate sustainability as a core analytic from which to observe processes of traditional culinary transformation, rather than as a constraint
4. Maintain methodological and platform flexibility that mirrors its subject

The **first** core recommendation is to avoid operationalising typicality as a rigid normative tool. Throughout our research, a recurrent theme was the risk of falling into what we call *gastro-fundamentalism*: an attitude that treats culinary traditions as fixed, pure or inviolable, policing any deviation from a supposedly authentic form.

Historical studies show that narratives of purity and authenticity often emerge precisely when traditions are under pressure, and the rise of digital food cultures can accelerate these tendencies by promoting idealised or nostalgic versions of “traditional foods” that do not reflect their actual historical variability.

Gastro-fundamentalism represents a conceptual hazard for a project like RELISH because it undermines two of the key findings established in D4.2:

1. Typicality is dynamic, constructed through communal practice and shaped by evolving social and environmental conditions
2. Sustainable adaptation must be integrated into the life of culinary traditions if they are to remain viable in the context of climate change

A gastro-fundamentalist interpretation of typicality would obscure these realities by encouraging rigid notions of identity, preventing meaningful adaptation, and excluding the very communities whose practices the platform aims to represent.

To counter this, the criteria developed in this report recommend understanding typicality as a **pattern of relations**, one where cultural artefacts and practices remain recognisable yet open to transformation. The platform should emphasise the historical evolution of recipes, the plurality of existing versions, and the creative capacity of communities to reinterpret their culinary heritage. This approach aligns with the ontological and historical analysis presented earlier in the report. It also encourages users to understand typicality as a **shared cultural achievement**.

This notion of gastro-fundamentalism is closely connected to a broader cultural phenomenon that contemporary scholarship has described as *gastronativism*, particularly in the work of Fabio Parasecoli (2022). Gastronativism refers to the ways groups mobilise food, including its traditions, images and narratives, to advance political agendas related to national or cultural identity. The concept highlights how food can become a symbolic resource used to define boundaries between “us” and “them,” reinforcing exclusionary narratives or essentialist visions of belonging. While gastronativism often arises in explicitly political contexts, its mechanisms are relevant to our framework. Both gastro-fundamentalism and gastronativism rely on idealised versions of culinary heritage that deny historical complexity and marginalise the adaptive practices that have always characterised food cultures.

Recognising these risks is crucial for RELISH. If the platform inadvertently reinforces nostalgic or purist narratives, it may likely contribute to socio-political dynamics that are beyond the scope of its mission. Instead, our findings suggest that the platform emphasises the historical evolution of recipes, the plurality of existing versions, and the creative capacity of communities to reinterpret their culinary heritage.

A **second** recommendation concerns **dissemination**. Academic research on food, whether historical, philosophical, anthropological or environmental, tends to reach a limited audience. One of the stated ambitions of RELISH is to engage younger generations who experience food culture through globalised media ecosystems, digital platforms, and social networks.

For this reason, the insights developed in WP4 must not remain confined to scholarly circles. The consortium should produce materials that translate the conceptual work of typicality and sustainability into accessible formats, such as short videos, interactive explanations, visual narratives, and digital storytelling adapted for platforms where younger people already engage with food content.

If younger people are to understand typicality as something dynamic, culturally meaningful and environmentally responsible, the platform must communicate these ideas in ways that resonate with their everyday digital practices. This includes foregrounding stories of adaptation, highlighting sustainable substitutions with clear explanations, and presenting narratives that honour tradition without isolating it

from contemporary challenges. WPs should coordinate to ensure that the insights gathered here shape the communication strategy of RELISH as a whole.

Furthermore, engagement with younger publics can serve as an ongoing source of **empirical input**. User interaction data, feedback from digital workshops, and participatory storytelling can inform later refinements of the platform, ensuring that it reflects the lived realities of its intended beneficiaries. The platform could thus serve as an archive of European culinary heritage and, at the same time, as a participatory space where heritage is interpreted, adapted and transmitted across present and future generations.

A **third** recommendation involves the continued integration of sustainability into the operational logic of the platform. As WP7&8 develop technical infrastructures, sustainability should be a fundamental axis of analysis. Environmental transformations affecting agriculture, shifts in suitable growing zones, water stress, biodiversity loss, and changing availability of animal products would be presented not as threats to tradition but as contexts out of which traditions evolve.

Findings suggest that younger users in particular are receptive to narratives that bridge heritage with environmental responsibility. We recommend that the platform provide clear, contextual explanations about how sustainable substitutions work, why they may be necessary, and how communities historically adapted to similar constraints. This framing positions sustainability in continuity with the adaptive capacity that has always characterised culinary traditions.

Fourth and final recommendation: it is essential to maintain the methodological flexibility that WP4 has established. Typicality will continue to evolve in response to cultural, economic and environmental forces, and the platform must remain open to incorporating new insights and adaptation scenarios. The criteria developed here represent a framework to be tested, refined and expanded as RELISH progresses.

6 Conclusions

D4.2 outlines rationale, context, input gathering, and review for generating preliminary frameworks and recommended criteria for operationalising two concepts: *typicality* and *sustainability*.

The report likewise identifies a set of risks: essentialism and gastro-fundamentalism. These risks are those which can misrepresent and thus further alienate or exclude relevant stakeholders, especially young adults living in Europe, from participating in and enacting culinary practices tied to culinary Intangible Culture Heritage.

These insights were drawn from a range of consultations, expertise, and collaborative iteration from internal and external discussion, collated and distilled in a set of visual figures and recommendations.

Taken together, these recommendations, concepts, and criteria for operationalisation offer a path forward that better represents culinary heritage, particularly its transformations in contemporary ecological and social realities. D4.2 will contribute to shaping the RELISH platform as a responsive repository of tradition and a catalyst for responsible innovation. Overall, the report aims to ensure that typicality remains a meaningful and dynamic dimension of European food culture.

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Suggested further reading

The works summarised above represent a selection from a wider body of literature that UMIL consulted while developing this framework. The titles below were part of that broader reading and are offered as further reading for partners who wish to explore the foundations of the argument in more depth.

- Bessière, Jacinthe. 1998. "Local Development and Heritage: Traditional Food and Cuisine as Tourist Attractions in Rural Areas." *Sociologia Ruralis* 38 (1): 21–34.
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Annex I: Criteria for Evaluating Typicality and Sustainability

The annex included in this document offers a structured synthesis of the conceptual tools developed in WP4 to operationalise typicality and sustainability in culinary recipes. While the main body of the report presents a philosophical and historical analysis, the tables below translate these insights into practical evaluative criteria.

Together, these tables serve as a reference system, clarifying how typicality emerges through sensory, procedural, narrative, and contextual dimensions, and they outline the conditions under which sustainable adaptation aligns with cultural meaning. They also highlight the risks of *gastro-fundamentalism* and *gastronativism*, offering conceptual safeguards against essentialist or exclusionary uses of food heritage. The annex sections should therefore be read as tools intended for conceptual clarity and practical implementation in the RELISH platform’s design.

Criteria for Evaluating Typicality

CRITERION	OPERATIONAL DESCRIPTION	PURPOSE FOR W7&8
Relational integrity	The recipe preserves the underlying relational pattern of ingredients, techniques, and meanings recognised by the community	Supports modelling of “recipe identity” relationships
Historical continuity	Aligns with historically documented practices, accepting variation across periods	Helps flag historically grounded versions in the database
Core ingredients (<i>anchors</i>)	Ingredients perceived as central to the identity and recognisability of the recipe, identified through cultural salience, free-list methodologies, or resistance to substitution	Allows identification of non-negotiable elements in ontology
Procedural fidelity	Preservation of characteristic techniques, textures, or preparation steps	Guides classification of procedural constraints in recipes
Sensory recognition	Recognition through key flavour, aroma, or visual markers	Supports sensory metadata and recognisability modelling
Contextuality	Maintains links to traditional contexts (festivals, rituals, social uses)	Enables contextual tagging of recipes in the platform
Narrative significance	Continues to embody community stories, memories, or symbolic meanings	Helps integrate narrative modules
Cognitive prototypicality	Degree to which a recipe variant conforms to culturally shared mental representations and graded category membership judgments	Informs recommendation logic for typical variants

CRITERION	OPERATIONAL DESCRIPTION	PURPOSE FOR W7&8
Ingredient centrality	Degree to which an ingredient contributes to perceived category identity and recognisability, measured through cultural salience and substitution resistance	Supports adaptive recommendation systems and substitution thresholds
Adaptive capacity	Able to evolve responsibly under environmental or social pressures	Assists in modelling sustainable variants
Acceptance by practitioners	The community perceives the version as legitimate and coherent	Validates platform suggestions against cultural norms

Criteria for Evaluating Sustainability

CRITERION	OPERATIONAL DESCRIPTION	PURPOSE FOR W7&8
Ecological impact	Evaluates greenhouse gases, water use, biodiversity effects, and resource intensity	Enables sustainability scoring modules
Local availability	Preference for ingredients suited to local climates, soils and seasons	Supports localisation options for users' regions
Substitution logic	Replacement ingredients should preserve functional, sensory, or symbolic roles within the relational structure of the recipe	Helps platform propose culturally coherent and psychologically acceptable sustainable alternatives
Functional role preservation	Substitutions maintain the culinary function of the original ingredient (for example protein component, aromatic base, binding agent, sauce element)	Supports structurally coherent recipe adaptation
Adaptive thresholds	Degree of variation tolerated before a recipe is no longer perceived as belonging to the same culinary category	Assists recommendation systems in modelling acceptable limits of modification
Cultural rigidity	Degree to which communities resist modifications affecting central recipe components	Enables culturally sensitive adaptation strategies
Procedural preservation	Maintains core cooking techniques even when ingredients change	Protects procedural identity while allowing adaptation
Sensory continuity	Adapted recipe retains recognisable sensory cues	Avoids recommending substitutions that break recognisability
Cultural acceptability	The community perceives the substitution as coherent and respectful	Ensures cultural sensitivity in substitution suggestions

CRITERION	OPERATIONAL DESCRIPTION	PURPOSE FOR W7&8
Socio-environmental embeddedness	Considers ecological systems, labour conditions, and production contexts	Assists WP7 in representing broader sustainability contexts
Low-impact variants	Uses plant-based or locally adapted low-impact ingredients	Enables “light-footprint” recipe suggestions
Adaptive resilience	Ability of a recipe to evolve responsibly without losing identity	Helps classify recipes by adaptation potential